

Silicon-Proven Low-Dropout Regulator Designed in 65nm CMOS Technology

David Maljar

Dep. of IC design and Test
Slovak University of Technology
Bratislava, Slovakia
david.maljar@stuba.sk

Róbert Ondica

Dep. of IC design and Test
Slovak University of Technology
Bratislava, Slovakia
robert.ondica@stuba.sk

Daniel Arbet

Dep. of IC design and Test
Slovak University of Technology
Bratislava, Slovakia
daniel.arbet@stuba.sk

Martin Kováč

Dep. of IC design and Test
Slovak University of Technology
Bratislava, Slovakia
martin_kovac@stuba.sk

Viera Stopjaková

Dep. of IC design and Test
Slovak University of Technology
Bratislava, Slovakia
viera.stopjakova@stuba.sk

Abstract—This work presents the 1.2 V Low-Dropout Regulator (LDO) designed in a standard 65nm CMOS technology using data obtained from experimental verification of 9 prototype chips. The measurement of standard parameters that were evaluated included Load Regulation (LDR) in the output current I_{OUT} range from 1 μA to 300 μA , Line Regulation (LNR) at I_{OUT} of 100 μA and 300 μA , Drop-Out voltage and PSRR parameter. In addition, the presented LDO dispose of a Slew-Rate Enhancement function, which can be activated externally. In all cases of this feature activation, the measurement proved its expected and correct function with reducing the settling time value and, depending on the direction of the output current change, also the voltage value for overshoot or undershoot.

Keywords—Low-Dropout Regulator, silicon-proven, Load Regulation, Line Regulation, Drop-Out voltage, PSRR, analog design, CMOS

I. INTRODUCTION

In today's era of electronic miniaturization, designers (especially analog ones) of integrated circuits (ICs) have to deal with various challenges such as reducing the supply voltage V_{DD} , and at the same time, reducing the area of the whole system on chip (SoC). In addition to the precise design of ICs (e.g. OPAMPs, voltage and current references, oscillators, LDOs, active and passive filters, etc.), they have to take into account that despite all successful simulations, whether Corner or Monte Carlo analysis, the reality may be slightly different in terms of the required parameters. Simulators are powerful design tools but still represent an approximation of reality. They can predict the behavior of ICs very accurately, and allow verification of the most important parameters (for example, in OPAMPs, these include DC gain, offset, bias currents, phase and gain margins) with a large number of necessary iterations. However, the main drawback is that simulation is based on device models used that are only statistically fitted, not exact. This includes the fact that it is very difficult to simulate properties such as aging of individual ICs to examine the behavior of circuits that operate in sub-threshold regime at the transistor level, or if they operate with

leakage currents. Evaluation of ICs by measurement is the only way to prove that an IC actually works under real-world conditions, and it can also reveal die-to-die variations of parameters. That is the reason why it is not just important, it is indispensable.

The results presented in this work concern an LDO circuit designed in standard 65nm CMOS technology, which parameters and properties were experimentally verified by measurement of 9 prototype chips. Since LDO circuit represents one of the basic building blocks in many SoCs, it is very useful to have it as a reliable and guaranteed functional device within the given requirements. Use of an LDO circuit lies primarily in providing low-noise and well-regulated supply voltage for circuits sensitive to switching noise such as Phase-Lock Loops (PLLs), Delay-Lock Loops (DLLs), ADCs, DACs, RF front-ends, etc. It provides a sufficiently high value of the PSRR parameter at low to mid frequencies, so it can isolate them from the global noisy V_{DD} . Another advantage of this circuit is its use when it is necessary to create multiple supply voltage domains (for example, creating supplies 1.0 V, 0.8 V, etc. from the global 1.5 V power supply) on a single SoC consisting of mixed-signal circuits. Compared to a switching regulator, which needs a high-quality inductor (large and lossy), and also creates electromagnetic interference (EMI), the LDO approach only needs capacitors, the value of which should create a compromise between its correct function and the chip area used. Last but not least, its on-chip presence eliminates external linear regulators.

As already mentioned, the key parameters for LDO include PSRR, LDR, and LNR, but also Drop-out voltage at a specific value of I_{OUT} and its time characteristics defining the slew-rate parameter through settling time, overshoot/undershoot at a specific change in I_{OUT} is important. In Section II, we describe the conceptual circuit diagram of the presented LDO circuit. Section III offers a clear treatment of the measurement results. In section IV, summary of achieved results along with a comparison to other works through the derived Figure of Merit (FOM) parameter based on the main parameters as PSRR, I_{LOAD} , drop-out voltage and C_{LOAD} , are presented.

Fig. 1: Conceptual topology of the proposed LDO circuit.

II. PROPOSED LDO CIRCUIT

A. Circuit topology

In Fig. 1, the topology of developed LDO circuit is shown. Previously, a similar topology was presented by this research team in [1], design of which was based on works [2]–[4]. In this work, slew-rate enhancement is also designed that was inspired by [3]. In the topology presented in this work, one of the differences compared to our previous research in [1] is the design of a 4-transistor voltage reference (V_{ref} block in Fig. 1), which according to simulations, generates a voltage of $100 \text{ mV} \pm 5\%$ at its output within all corners. In terms of improving the PSRR parameter, a cascode transistor M_{N1} is again added next to the PMOS pass device M_{P1} (which is driven by differential common-gate source-cross-coupled error amplifier). The improvement over the original research consists in the elimination of 4 resistors $R_{D1} - R_{D4}$, which, together with other circuits, set and ensured the voltage conditions for controlling the cascode transistor M_{N1} , thus saving the chip area. The LDO topology in [1] worked on the principle of maintaining a constant voltage V_{DS_NMOS} , while voltage V_{LOCAL} was influenced by the Tunable Buffer 2. The LDO presented here works on the principle of maintaining a constant voltage V_{LOCAL} . Signal V_{REF} is multiplied by Tunable Buffer 1 as needed. The voltage V_{REF_BUFF1} enters the OPAMP, which controls NMOS device M_{N1} while under ideal conditions, the equality between these voltages applies:

$$V_{REF_BUFF1} = V_{LOCAL}. \quad (1)$$

The use of a charge pump with the low-pass filter to supply the OPAMP allows generating a voltage on the gate of M_{N1} higher than V_{IN} , which is necessary for its reliable switching-on. In addition, transistor

M_{N1} must be kept in saturation under all operating conditions. The output voltage of the LDO circuit was set to 1.2 V, and the input voltage range is from 1.3 V to 2.1 V (due to the charge pump). Since the purpose is to use the LDO circuit in ultra-low-voltage applications, the output current range was required from $1 \mu\text{A}$ to $300 \mu\text{A}$ with a dropout voltage of 100 mV (in the worst case).

Fig. 2 shows the schematic diagram of the slew-rate enhancement block (see Fig. 1). The output current of this block depends on the LDO output current flowing through the PMOS device M_{P1} . A copy of this current is created by transistor M_{P2} . In our research, the mirror ratio between M_{P2} and M_{P1} is set to 1:60, which was sufficient. By reducing the mirror ratio we again save certain area on the chip. Next, the current through the non-inverting stage, formed by transistor M_{N6} , is mirrored through the transistors M_{P3} and M_{P4} to transistor M_{N3} . Transistors M_{N2} and M_{N3} create a current mirror with a ratio of 1:10. In this way, M_{N2} can sink 10% of the output load current and improve the transient recovery of the entire LDO [1].

Fig. 2: Topology of slew-rate enhancement circuit.

B. Layout

Fig. 3 shows layout of the proposed LDO circuit from Fig. 1. As one can observe, area of the entire circuit occupies $48.853 \cdot 10^3 \mu\text{m}^2$ with dimensions $250.4 \mu\text{m} \times 195.1 \mu\text{m}$. The largest block in terms of area is Tunable Buffer 1 with dimensions $129.8 \mu\text{m} \times 61.2 \mu\text{m}$ ($7.944 \cdot 10^3 \mu\text{m}^2$), which is mainly occupied by large on-chip NMOS capacitors to improve its PSRR parameter, as it is directly supplied from V_{IN} (V_{DD}) and it accounts for 16.26 % of the total chip area.

Fig. 3: Layout of the proposed LDO circuit.

III. ACHIEVED RESULTS

Developed LDO circuit was fabricated in 65nm CMOS process. To evaluate the main parameters and properties, 9 prototyped chip samples we measured. Fig. 4 shows the measurement results of the LDR parameter. The entire characteristics were measured in the range of output currents from $1 \mu\text{A}$ to $300 \mu\text{A}$. As can be observed in Fig. 4, the dependences for all 9 prototype chips have decreasing trend, while change in the output voltage V_{OUT} is in order of mV.

Fig. 4: Load regulation of the proposed LDO circuit.

In Fig. 5 and Fig. 6, the LNR characteristics at the output currents of $100 \mu\text{A}$ and $300 \mu\text{A}$ are depicted, respectively. It is rather obvious from both dependences that V_{OUT} can be considered as a constant voltage value of 1.2 V, since its range again varies by

an order of magnitude in mV for all 9 prototype samples. In the case of dependences for $I_{OUT} = 100 \mu\text{A}$, reliable regulation of the output voltage V_{OUT} was measured from the value $V_{IN} = 1.3 \text{ V}$ to 2.14 V , which is in accordance with the design requirements. In the case of curves for $I_{OUT} = 300 \mu\text{A}$, reliable regulation of V_{OUT} was measured from a slightly lower V_{IN} value in the range from 1.28 V to 2.1 V .

Fig. 5: Line regulation, $I_{OUT} = 100 \mu\text{A}$.

Fig. 6: Line regulation, $I_{OUT} = 300 \mu\text{A}$.

Fig. 7 shows the PSRR parameter curves in the frequency range from 100 Hz to 10 MHz for $I_{OUT} = 100 \mu\text{A}$. It is obvious that these curves of all chip samples have approximately the same nature. At the frequency of 100 Hz, the best case of the PSRR value was measured on chip 7 with -71.4 dB , while the worst case was represented by the chip 5 with the value of -48.1 dB . All curves from low frequencies acquires an increasing trend (deterioration of PSRR) to the frequency value of approximately 25 kHz. Up to 1 MHz value, the characteristics are slightly scattered within die-to-die. At 1 MHz, the PSRR best case value -28.2 dB was measured on chip 8, while the worst case was reported for chip 1 with the value of 15.9 dB .

Fig. 8 and Fig. 9 show the transfer characteristics for $I_{OUT} = 100 \mu\text{A}$ and $300 \mu\text{A}$, respectively. The LDO is in the off region until a voltage equal to approximately 0.9 V. Then, the dropout region ends approximately between 1.22-1.25 V, which represents V_{DD_MIN} . In both graphs, one can observe that for each prototype chip, the design conditions for output voltage regulation from $V_{IN} = 1.3 \text{ V}$ were met.

Fig. 7: PSRR parameter of the proposed LDO circuit, $I_{OUT} = 100 \mu A$.

Fig. 8: Transfer characteristic, $I_{OUT} = 100 \mu A$.

Fig. 9: Transfer characteristic, $I_{OUT} = 300 \mu A$.

Tab. I. shows a summary of the Drop-out voltage V_{DO} parameter of the proposed LDO for all prototype chips. At $I_{OUT} = 100 \mu A$, the lowest value of this voltage was measured on chip 4 with 12.86 mV, the highest on chip 2 with 40.45 mV. At $I_{OUT} = 300 \mu A$, the lowest value was measured on chip 9 with 32.10 mV, while the highest on chip 1 with 63.04 mV.

	Drop-out voltage [mV]	
	$I_{LOAD} = 100 \mu A$	$I_{LOAD} = 300 \mu A$
Chip 1	39.07	63.04
Chip 2	40.45	62.11
Chip 3	20.28	39.00
Chip 4	12.86	38.95
Chip 5	16.63	39.65
Chip 6	13.28	38.61
Chip 7	38.98	53.65
Chip 8	39.43	40.18
Chip 9	12.90	32.10
Average	25.99	45.26

TABLE I: Drop-out voltage of the proposed LDO.

Tab. II. offers an overview of the main static parameters of the circuit such as V_{DD_MIN} , LNR and LDR. At $I_{OUT} = 100 \mu A$, the lowest V_{DD_MIN} value was measured on chip 5 with 1.21 V, the highest on chip 2 with 1.23 V. At $I_{OUT} = 300 \mu A$, the lowest value of this parameter was measured on chip 4 with 1.23 V and the highest on chip 7 with 1.26 V. In terms of percentage expression of the LNR parameter, its lowest value was measured on chip 2 with 0.073 ($I_{OUT} = 100 \mu A$) and chip 9 with 0.054 ($I_{OUT} = 300 \mu A$). On the contrary, the highest values were measured on chip 8 with 0.115 ($I_{OUT} = 100 \mu A$) and chip 5 with 1.148 ($I_{OUT} = 300 \mu A$). The lowest value of LDR parameter is represented by chip 1 with 24.626 mV/mA, while the highest is represented by chip 3 with 39.021 mV/mA. The only one of the parameters presented as simulated data is the quiescent current. This current could not be measured for the proposed LDO circuit due to its internal circuitry within the SoC in the specific application.

Results presented in Table III. and Table IV. compare load transient responses depending on the activated slew-rate enhancement subcircuit. From the above summaries it can be observed that for both output current step functions $1 \mu A \rightarrow 100 \mu A$ and vice versa there was an improvement of all parameters – Settling Time, Over/Undershoot and also the Slew-Rate. With current step upwards, the average settling

TABLE II: Main static properties of the proposed LDO.

	Minimum Supply Voltage [V]		Quiescent Current [μA]	LNR [%]		LDR [mV/mA]	Area [μm^2]
	100 μA	300 μA		100 μA	300 μA		
Chip 1	1.2311	1.2551	4.2*	0.113	0.117	24.626	48.853 10^3
Chip 2	1.2325	1.2544		0.073	0.072	30.429	
Chip 3	1.2077	1.2298		0.078	0.140	39.021	
Chip 4	1.2077	1.2297		0.046	0.088	30.340	
Chip 5	1.2074	1.2309		0.108	1.148	29.729	
Chip 6	1.2064	1.2301		0.048	0.076	24.687	
Chip 7	1.2328	1.2555		0.097	0.092	29.674	
Chip 8	1.2309	1.2309		0.115	0.120	29.667	
Chip 9	1.2081	1.2309		0.075	0.054	33.599	
Average	1.2183	1.2386	0.0837	0.2119	30.1969		

* Simulated result.

TABLE III: Main dynamic parameter of the LDO with SR enhancement OFF.

	Load Transient Response, SR enhancement OFF					
	1 μA \rightarrow 100 μA			100 μA \rightarrow 1 μA		
	Settling Time [μs]	Overshoot [mV]	SR [$\mu\text{V/S}$]	Settling Time [μs]	Undershoot [mV]	SR [$\mu\text{V/S}$]
Chip 1	55.80	55.3672	58.8505	12.70	-108.5230	80.4829
Chip 2	63.10	63.0234	60.8203	12.80	-120.2420	94.9222
Chip 3	76.50	67.7422	70.1116	31.30	-128.8050	100.5236
Chip 4	59.90	56.7266	61.8527	15.00	-110.7500	94.7362
Chip 5	62.80	52.4922	62.3958	14.90	-97.0156	87.2851
Chip 6	86.30	55.6484	71.6028	11.60	-108.6020	95.3616
Chip 7	87.00	70.8672	74.7005	10.40	-130.5470	102.8561
Chip 8	99.80	82.8281	79.1407	10.40	-147.3130	108.3330
Chip 9	81.30	75.1688	73.2049	12.50	-125.2580	99.5136
Average	74.7222	64.4293	68.0756	14.6222	-119.6728	96.0016

TABLE IV: Main dynamic parameters of LDO with SR enhancement ON.

	Load Transient Response, SR enhancement ON					
	1 μA \rightarrow 100 μA			100 μA \rightarrow 1 μA		
	Settling Time [μs]	Overshoot [mV]	SR [$\mu\text{V/S}$]	Settling Time [μs]	Undershoot [mV]	SR [$\mu\text{V/S}$]
Chip 1	38.00	11.8906	19.4531	12.00	-26.2266	18.5511
Chip 2	35.70	12.4844	31.0156	7.30	-29.5859	19.3359
Chip 3	53.60	11.7734	20.5079	11.90	-26.2422	16.1478
Chip 4	34.40	9.3281	27.5467	7.30	-22.8437	14.7686
Chip 5	48.50	13.1562	32.7656	8.40	-27.1016	21.3672
Chip 6	65.60	6.8828	25.7344	8.10	-15.2422	10.5382
Chip 7	35.40	8.7578	30.4844	10.30	-21.7734	13.9964
Chip 8	85.40	17.5706	29.1699	8.20	-30.9219	21.5057
Chip 9	72.80	15.5548	25.5914	10.20	-28.2516	17.2716
Average	52.1556	11.9332	28.0300	9.30	-25.3543	17.0536

time value was improved from 74.72 μs to 52.16 μs , the overshoot value from 64.43 mV to 11.94 mV, and the SR parameter from 68.08 $\mu\text{V/s}$ to 28.03 $\mu\text{V/s}$. Similarly, during a downward current change, the average settling time value was reduced from 14.62 μs to 9.30 μs , the undershoot value from -119.67 mV to -25.35 mV, and the SR parameter from 96 $\mu\text{V/s}$ to 17.05 $\mu\text{V/s}$. In Fig. 10, screenshot of transient responses from an oscilloscope is shown.

Fig. 10: Transient response, $I_{OUT} = 100 \mu\text{A}$.

IV. DISCUSSION & CONCLUSION

Tab. V. shows a comparison of the achieved results of this work with other works. From this summary, a significant contribution of the proposed LDO can be observed. In terms of the total chip area occupied, this LDO is among the smallest circuits with the area of 0.048 mm^2 . Compared to other works, it has also the lowest Drop-out voltage value of approximately 45 mV, while it should be noted that this is the average value of 9 prototype chip samples at the maximum output current of 300 μA . Another essential feature of our circuit is its quiescent current value of approximately 4.2 μA , which is a consequence of the fact that it is an ultra-low voltage design. Compared to other works, the LDO reliably works with a low value of the output capacitor C_{LOAD} , which ranges from 100 pF and 200 pF. For a quantifiable comparison of individual works, a Figure of Merit (FOM) was derived, which relates PSRR at 1 MHz, output current I_{LOAD} , drop-out voltage V_{DO} and output capacitor C_{LOAD} . The following applies:

$$FOM = \frac{|PSRR@1MHz| I_{LOAD}}{V_{DO} C_{LOAD}}. \quad (2)$$

TABLE V: Comparison of the proposed LDO circuit with other works.

Reference	[5]	[6]	[7]	[8]	[9]	This work
Year	2018	2020	2020	2021	2024	2025
Technology [nm]	65	180	40	65	65	65
Area [mm^2]	0.048	0.12	0.05	0.08	0.039	0.048
Power Transistor	PMOS	PMOS	PMOS	PMOS	PMOS	PMOS+NMOS
V_{OUT} [V]	1.0	4.5	5	1.8	1.8	1.2
Drop-out voltage	>0.2	>0.178	0.3	>0.2	0.2	0.045
I_Q [μA]	40	5.6-35	150	5	82-110	4.2
I_{LOAD_MAX} [mA]	100	250	200	100	50	0.3
C_{LOAD} μF	4.7	1-12	0.5-2	1-12	0.01	0.0001-0.0002
PSRR [dB]						
@ 100 kHz	-89	-77	-75	-77	-91	-20
@ 1 MHz	-70	-72	-58	-85	-82	-15
FOM	7447	101124	77333	42500	2050000	1000000

The goal is to achieve the highest possible numerical value of the defined FOM. The essence of an LDO design is to have the highest possible PSRR, the largest possible output current, and at the same time, the lowest values of V_{DO} and C_{LOAD} . In terms of the other parameters, the developed LDO circuit has an average value of the minimum supply voltage V_{DD_MIN} of 1.22 V and 1.24 V at $I_{LOAD} = 100 \mu\text{A}$ and $I_{LOAD} = 300 \mu\text{A}$, respectively. At these currents (100 μA and 300 μA , respectively), the line regulation reached the values of 0.084% and 0.212%. The average load regulation value of all measured chips is 30.2 mV/mA. For low-voltage design, the PSRR parameter is considered sufficiently high, especially at low frequencies up to 1 MHz, despite the low numerical values. The fact that these values were sufficient even when using a small capacitor was demonstrated within the FOM parameter. The essential feature is the enhancement of Slew-Rate, which was confirmed for a step change of I_{LOAD} from 1 μA to 300 μA and vice versa. In any case, a reduced value of the SR parameter was recorded after activation of the subcircuit. The entire concept mentioned above was developed in our department for the application of a DC-DC converter. Based on the achieved results, it can be stated that the developed LDO circuit meets all design requirements.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work was supported in part by the Scientific Grant Agency VEGA under grant No. 1/0705/24, and the Slovak Research and Development Agency under grants APVV-23-0071 and VV-MVP-24-0313. This work has also received funding from the Chips Joint Undertaking under grant agreement number 101139790 and its members, including the top-up funding by Germany, Italy, Slovakia, Spain and The Netherlands. This research was done in the framework of "Matching" Grant No. 09I01-03-V04-00108 from Recovery and Resilience Plan for the Slovak Republic.

REFERENCES

- [1] D. Arbet, M. Kováč, D. Maljar, L. Nagy, and V. Stopjaková, "High power supply rejection ldo regulator for switching applications," in *2022 45th Jubilee International Convention on Information, Communication and Electronic Technology (MIPRO)*, pp. 162–167, 2022.
- [2] T. Y. Man, P. K. T. Mok, and M. Chan, "A high slew-rate push-pull output amplifier for low-quiescent current low-dropout regulators with transient-response improvement," *IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems II: Express Briefs*, vol. 54, no. 9, pp. 755–759, 2007.
- [3] P. M. Furth, S. Krishnapurapu, S. H. Pakala, and M. A. Haque, "A 5.3 μA quiescent current fully-integrated low-dropout (ldo) regulator with transient recovery time enhancement," in *2013 IEEE 56th International Midwest Symposium on Circuits and Systems (MWSCAS)*, pp. 9–12, 2013.
- [4] H. Valapala and P. M. Furth, "Analysis and design of fully integrated very low quiescent current ldos," 2012.
- [5] J. Jiang, W. Shu, and J. S. Chang, "A 65-nm cmos low dropout regulator featuring ≥ 60 -db psrr over 10-mhz frequency range and 100-ma load current range," *IEEE Journal of Solid-State Circuits*, vol. 53, no. 8, pp. 2331–2342, 2018.
- [6] K. Joshi, S. Manandhar, and B. Bakaloglu, "A 5.6 u a wide bandwidth, high power supply rejection linear low-dropout regulator with 68 db of psr up to 2 mhz," *IEEE Journal of Solid-State Circuits*, vol. 55, no. 8, pp. 2151–2160, 2020.
- [7] C. Azcona and S. Iriarte, "Compensation scheme for high bandwidth ldos with large parasitic esl," in *2020 IEEE 29th International Symposium on Industrial Electronics (ISIE)*, pp. 400–404, 2020.
- [8] H. H. Hammam, H. A. Omran, and S. A. Ibrahim, "Ultra-low-power low drop-out (ldo) voltage regulator with improved power supply rejection," in *2021 38th National Radio Science Conference (NRSC)*, vol. 1, pp. 177–185, 2021.
- [9] X. Cheng, H. Liu, J. Zhang, Y. Yu, Y. Wu, C. Zhao, and K. Kang, "A fast transient response capless ldo regulator achieving -78 db of psr up to 2 mhz," in *2024 IEEE International Symposium on Circuits and Systems (ISCAS)*, pp. 1–5, 2024.